

THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNAL FACTORS ON THE HEALTH OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15645456>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 01-iyun 2025 yil
Ma'qullandi: 03-iyun 2025 yil
Nashr qilindi: 11-iyun 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

School-age students, health,
diseases, indoor air.

ABSTRACT

The long stay of a large number of students in classes leads to the accumulation of anthropogenic substances and microorganisms. The concept of health reflects the quality of the body's adaptation to environmental conditions and is the result of human interaction with it. Hygienic assessment of microclimate parameters of school classrooms is the basis for predicting the health status and performance of students.

Relevance of the topic: According to the World Health Organization (WHO), health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or physical defects. The concept of health thus reflects the quality of the organism's adaptation to environmental conditions and the result of the process of human interaction with the environment. According to WHO, 4.3 million people die annually due to air pollution (WHO, 2018). An analysis of mortality in Russian cities shows that the greatest correlation between mortality from cardiovascular diseases is observed with air pollution

WHO recommends that Member States improve epidemiological surveillance of air pollution-related diseases and establish air quality monitoring systems and health registries to implement indoor air quality guidelines.

The coronavirus pandemic, which has changed almost all aspects of human and professional life, has drawn special attention to this issue. This situation has greatly affected the education system; under conditions of isolation and restrictions, thousands of educational institutions have switched to distance learning technologies, which has significantly contributed to the development of e-education.

However, distance learning has highlighted the need to maintain the role of the teacher and live communication with students in classrooms, as well as the inevitability of revising the content of education.

Objective: Development and implementation of hygiene recommendations aimed at improving school factors affecting the physical capabilities and health of students.

Research materials: The following data were used: indicators of student morbidity, their health status, conditions of the educational process (microclimate parameters, equipment,

quantity and size of dust particles, school schedule), anthropometric indicators (chest circumference, height, weight).

Research results: As is known, carbon dioxide (CO₂) belongs to the 4th hazard class and is considered relatively safe, but its concentration in the air correlates with the levels of other pollutants. The CO₂ concentration in the room should not exceed 0.1% (1%), which is the maximum permissible concentration. The studies were conducted in the center of the classroom at a height of 1.5 m from the floor before and after the classes. The experiment found that 26.1% of classrooms had low CO₂ levels before classes began, but by the end of classes the number of classrooms with poor air quality had increased to 67%. More than half of the classrooms (56.2%) had their windows and doors completely closed during classes, with the average CO₂ level in the air in these classrooms being 1256.1 ppm (the average was 3041 ppm).

The study also found that the prevalence of asthma in children was significantly associated with urinary formaldehyde levels, indicating harmful exposure to chemical pollutants.

Conclusion: Environmental factors, the state of the natural environment around the school, significantly affect the health of both current and future students and teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the requirements for preventive and health-improving activities of educational institutions, as well as to ensure regular ventilation of premises and control over air quality in educational institutions.

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